

MECHANISM OF LUMINESCENCE OF CARBON MATERIALS

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NAO "L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University",
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The article proposes a new mechanism for the occurrence of luminescence in graphite and graphene when excited by an electric field, laser, or external deformation. Most authors believe that there are two mechanisms in graphite that emit photons with a broadband spectrum. When graphite is excited by an electric current, radiation similar to thermal radiation occurs. When graphite is excited by a laser, anti-Stokes luminescence occurs. In a number of studies, photoluminescence of the forbidden band of carbon nanotubes was discovered. The observed luminescence of graphene is explained in terms of the mechanism of hot luminescence. A common characteristic of the radiation of carbon materials is broadband spectra, the causes of which are still not clear. A discrete system is responsible for the luminescence of graphite, which is in three electronic states - the ground, excited, and a state with separated charges. It is the processes of separation and recombination of charges that represent the luminescence process. The process of charge separation itself is inherent in the non-equilibrium of the nuclear subsystem, associated with the deformation of the crystal lattice due to the reconstruction of the graphite surface. This means that the glow of graphite, graphene and nanotubes, like hot luminescence, is carried out by converting the energy of surface deformation into the glow of a defect-free crystal.

Keywords: graphite, graphene, carbon, model, surface layer, crystal, nanostructure, luminescence

Introduction

Carbon structure photonics [1] complements silicon photonics [2] in terms of graphene-based active materials, which can provide a leading platform for the development of two-dimensional (2D), flexible, thin and reliable light sources [3]. Graphene-based light-emitting devices can be considered for future applications such as optical modulators, optical interconnects and optical sensing [3, 4]. The global photonics market will exceed \$1.3 trillion by 2028, with China leading the way. Carbon structure photonics began in 2002 with the introduction of the term "Carbon NanoWalls",

meaning carbon nanowalls, carbon sheets, nanocrystalline graphite, etc. [5]. The broadband emission of polycrystalline graphite was studied in [6]. The emission spectra of graphite were obtained using resistive and laser excitation methods. It is shown that there are two mechanisms in graphite by which photons with a broadband spectrum are emitted. When graphite is excited by an electric current, radiation similar to thermal radiation occurs. When graphite is excited by a laser, anti-Stokes luminescence occurs (Fig. 1a). A red shift in the emission spectrum was found for finely dispersed graphite (Fig. 1b).

Figure 1. Laser (1) and resistive (2, 3, 4) emission spectra of massive graphite at different temperatures, as well as their comparison with the spectrum of a tungsten filament (5) (a); emission spectra of a massive sample (1) and a finely dispersed sample (2) of polycrystalline graphite (b) [6].

Electroluminescence of carbon structures has been investigated in many papers. In [7], blackbody emission from aligned multiwalled carbon nanotubes sub-

jected to field emission was observed. The light intensity correlates with the emission current fluctuations. The onset of light emission occurs at an emission current of 1 mA/cm² and corresponds to a temperature of

about 1550 K. Beyond this critical current, irreversible changes occur in the nanotube film. The correlation between light intensity and emission current provides convincing evidence of Joule heating and stable operation for nanotube temperatures of at least 2000 K and emission current densities of about 10 mA/cm².

In [8], household light bulbs were fabricated using macroscopically long and aligned single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWNTs) as filaments. It was found that the SWNT filament could emit bright light when an electric current was passed through it. The light spectrum from the SWNT filament showed a non-blackbody thermal emission characteristic, and its infrared emission was almost completely suppressed, possibly due to the

“photonic band gap” effect that occurs in the loose fibrous structure of the SWNT filament bundle. It was found that the electrical resistance of the SWNT filament first increased and then decreased continuously during light emission. It was also found that the electric current could cause the SWNT filament to degrade and burn out and lead to complete amorphization, and that the mushroom-shaped carbon structure was formed due to the evaporation of the carbon of the nanotube filament during light emission. In work [9] photoluminescence of the forbidden zone of carbon nanotubes was discovered (Fig. 2a). Analysis of photoluminescence of dissolved single-layer carbon tubes was carried out in work [10] (Fig. 2b).

Figure 2. Photoluminescence spectrum of suspended nanotubes. This spectrum was obtained in air at room temperature with 1.0 mW laser excitation at 532 nm [9] (a); photoluminescence spectrum of SWNT nanotubes from aqueous suspension [10] (b).

In the above-mentioned articles, the mechanism of exciton luminescence is used for the photoluminescence of SWNT nanotubes. In [11], a comparison of the electrical and optical characteristics of SWNT nanotubes was made. It was shown that the side bands in the

spectra of nanotubes are due to defects introduced by the interaction of the nanotube lattice with oxygen-containing end groups of the substrate surface. The electroluminescence spectra of graphene according to the data of [12-14] are shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Electroluminescence of graphene [12-14]

The observed luminescence of graphene is explained in terms of the hot luminescence mechanism. A common characteristic of the radiation of all carbon nanomaterials is broadband spectra, the causes of which are still not clear/

The purpose of this work is to propose a new mechanism for the occurrence of luminescence in graphite and graphene when excited by an electric field, laser or external deformation.

Thickness of the surface layer of graphite and graphene

For the thickness of the surface layer of a solid, the following formula was obtained [15]:

$$R(I) = \alpha \cdot \frac{v}{S} \tag{1}$$

Here $v = M/\rho$ (M is the molar mass, ρ is the density of the solid); $S = 1 \text{ m}^2$ is the area element; $\alpha = 0.17 \cdot 10^{-}$

⁹ mol. For graphite and graphene, the R(I) layer is presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Thickness of the surface layer of graphite and grapheme

Carbon	M, g/mol	ρ , g/sm ³	R(I) _a , nm	R(I) _c , nm	γ_a , mJ/m ²	γ_c , mJ/m ²
Graphite	12,0107	2,26	0.900 (3)	2.46 (3)	2195	130
Grapheme	12,0107	2,26	0,246 (1)	0,14 (1)	2652	-

In Table 1, the number in brackets represents the number of monolayers – $n = R(I)/a$ (a is the lattice constant). It is evident that the number of graphite monolayers is 3, which is confirmed experimentally (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Change in graphite parameters depending on the number of its layers [16].

Elastic parameters of graphene and graphite were determined by us in [17, 18].

Table 2.

Elastic parameters of graphite and grapheme

Carbon	W_{aa} , J/m ²	W_{ac} , J/m ²	σ_{isa} , GPa	σ_{isc} , GPa	E_a , GPa	E_c , GPa
Graphite	2,853	1,690	4,9	1,36	7,59	3,48
Grapheme	3,448	-	118,4	-	1000	-

In Table 2, W_a is the adhesion energy and E is the Young's modulus of elasticity. A schematic representation of equation (1) is shown in Fig. 5a, and Fig. 5b shows the corrugations on the graphene surface that

arise due to high internal stresses σ_{is} (Table 2). In the R(II) mesolayer, the structure is somewhat different than in the R(I) nanolayer and the bulk phase, due to the difference in size effects [15].

Figure 5. Solid state diagram: nanolayer → mesolayer → bulk phase (a); corrugated graphene (b).

Fig. 6 shows the crystal structure of graphite and grapheme.

Figure 6. Graphite crystal lattice (a); two-dimensional honeycomb graphene crystal lattice as a set of two interpenetrating sublattices A and B (b).

The carbon atom has three equivalent $\sigma_{x,y}$ -bonds located in one plane at an angle of 120° to each other. The p_z-orbital, which is not involved in hybridization and is located perpendicular to the plane of σ -bonds, is used to form π -bonds with other atoms. This is the geometry of carbon that is characteristic of graphite (sp²-hybridization).

Since the bonds acting in the basal planes (the bond energy is 420...460 kJ/mol) and the bonds between these basal planes (the bond energy is 42 kJ/mol)

are very different, there is a strong anisotropy of properties in single-crystal graphite, and this determines the properties and structure of polycrystalline graphites.

We will calculate the estimate of the deformation energy associated with the reconstruction of the surface of graphite and graphene using the formula:

$$E_d = \frac{1}{n} W_a \cdot R(I)^2 = W_a \cdot R(I) \cdot a, \quad (2)$$

where a is the lattice constant of graphite and graphene.

These data are shown in Table 3.

Table 3.

Deformation energy E_d of graphite and grapheme				
Carbon	$a_a, \text{Å}$	$a_c, \text{Å}$	E_{da}, eV	E_{dc}, eV
Graphite	2,46	6,71	2,27	1,42
Grapheme	2,46	1,41	1,62	-

We will represent a nanolayer with an area of $S = 1 \text{ m}^2$ and a size of $R(I)$ graphite as a nonlinear capacitor - a varicond (due to the presence of size effects) (Fig. 7a) on one of the plates of which large stresses σ is develop, leading to significant deformation energy E_d

(Table 3). This deformation energy first charges the capacitor, and then, under external influence (impact, friction, ultrasound, etc.), is discharged (Fig. 7b).

a)

b)

Figure 7. Varicond circuit (a); voltage change curves on the capacitor plates during its charging (1) and discharging (2) (b).

The deformation energy E_d is spent on heat, acoustic emission (propagation of sound waves), exoemission (emission of slow electrons and ions) and luminescence (see below).

Quantum structure of the surface layer of graphite and graphene

We will imagine the nanolayer in Fig. 5a as a potential well with infinitely high walls, then the energy levels $E_n(z)$ in it are equal to [19]:

$$E_n(z) = \frac{\hbar^2 \pi^2 n^2}{2m_e R(I)^2}, \quad (3)$$

These levels are shown in Fig. 8a taking into account Table 1. The E_n level can be represented by Landau levels (Fig. 8b). From equation (3) it follows that the energy levels E_n of the nanolayer are determined by one fundamental parameter – the constant of the metal crystal lattice a (this follows from $n = R(l)/a$ [20]:

$$E_n = \eta \cdot \frac{n^2}{l^2}, \quad (4)$$

where $\eta = \text{const.}$

Figure 8. Dependence of the energy level E_n in the nanolayer (a); quasi-discrete spectrum of electrons in the quantum well (b).

The lattice constant a changes in the $R(l)$ layer due to the reconstruction of the graphite surface. This means that graphite monolayers can be represented as quantum planes with energy E_n . As soon as the parameter a stops changing, the spectrum of quantum states becomes a continuous spectrum, where the classical Drude–Lorentz laws are satisfied for graphite.

It follows from Fig. 8a that the energy levels $E_n(\infty) = E_F$ is the Fermi energy level of graphite. In [21], the Fermi energy was calculated to be 1.5 eV for three-dimensional graphite and 2.0 eV for two-dimensional graphite. Since the surface layer of graphite is a two-dimensional medium, three quantum planes of graphite with \mathbf{a}_1 , \mathbf{a}_2 and \mathbf{a}_3 should be considered. The first monolayer of graphite, graphene, determines unique physical and chemical properties [22-25]. The motion of electrons in graphene is described by a two-component

equation similar to the Dirac equation [23]. If we look for a solution to the Dirac equation in the form of a harmonic wave, we obtain the dispersion law for massless particles (Fig. 9), and the solution itself has the form:

$$\tilde{N} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \pm e^{i\theta} \end{pmatrix} \cdot e^{i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{r}}, \quad \theta = \arctg(k_y / k_x). \quad (5)$$

The Fermi surface degenerates into the Dirac point, and the Fermi energy is $E_F = 0$. Thus, graphene is a single-layer 2D Dirac material, which is a quantum system at any temperature. The topological properties of graphene are due to the Dirac nature of the electron spectrum, which is similar to d-wave superconductors (cuprates, YBCO), which are also described by a massless Dirac Hamiltonian near the nodal points of the spectrum [26].

Figure 9. Electronic structure of graphene [23].

Bilayer graphene is different from monolayer graphene and graphite and exhibits improved physical,

chemical, electronic and optical properties compared to graphene and bulk graphite materials [27–29]. The

twisted bilayer graphene (tBLG) superlattice is formed when these layers are twisted at a small angle. The presence of disorder and interlayer interactions in tBLG improves several characteristics including optical and electrical properties. The studies of twisted bilayer graphene have been exciting and challenging so far, especially after the magic angle superconductivity was reported in tBLG [30]. Bilayer graphene can be considered as a “graphene + YBCO” system in the Landau–Zener model [31]. We show that the superconducting transition temperature will be:

$$\check{N}_{\check{n}} = \frac{E_F}{k \ln(k\tau/2)} = \delta \cdot E_F, \quad (6)$$

where $\delta = \text{const}$, which is quite difficult to determine theoretically.

For us, the most important thing here is the dependence of the superconducting transition temperature on the Fermi energy E_F , which can be changed, for example, using magnetic or electric fields, or by changing

the value of the magic angle. From Fig. 8a, taking into account the work [21], it follows that E_F for two-layer graphene is $E_F = 0.9 \text{ eV}$. In the work [32], for two-layer graphene, $T_c = 1.7 \text{ K}$ was obtained, which means that in (6) the value $\delta_1 = 1.9 \text{ K eV}^{-1}$.

Three-layer graphene differs from the last two in mobility and conductivity [33]. The peculiarity of three-layer graphene is that after it is twisted at the magic angle, it develops superconductivity, which withstands magnetic fields 2-3 times greater than the Pauli limit for spin-singlet pairing [34]. This case is similar to two-layer graphene, which can also be considered using the Landau–Zener Hamiltonian. From Fig. 8a, taking into account the work [21], it follows that the Fermi energy for three-layer graphene is $E_F = 1.2 \text{ eV}$. In [34], it was obtained for three-layer graphene that $T_c = 2.9 \text{ K}$, which means that in (6) the value $\delta_2 = 2.4 \text{ K eV}^{-1}$. Approximately, $\delta_1 = \delta_2 = 2 = \text{const}$ is satisfied. The diagram of three-layer graphene is shown in Fig. 10.

Figure 10. Schematic Dirac cones of three graphene layers in reciprocal space (a); enlarged image of separated Dirac cones of three graphene layers (b) [34].

Luminescence of graphite and graphene

As emphasized above, there is no clear idea about the luminescence of graphite and graphene. The surface layer of graphite is a quantum subsystem consisting of three graphene monolayers. The energy levels in this layer are a discrete system, the physical processes in which are different from the band states [35]. A discrete system is responsible for the luminescence of graphite, which is in three electronic states - the ground, excited, and the state with separated charges. It is the processes of charge separation and recombination that represent the luminescence process. The process of charge separation

itself is inherent in the nonequilibrium of the nuclear subsystem associated with the deformation of the crystal lattice due to the reconstruction of the graphite surface (Table 3). This means that the graphite glow is similar to hot luminescence [36] with a wavelength of radiation $\lambda = h c/E_d$, where $h c = 12.3 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ eV m}$. Taking from Table 3 E_d for graphite, we have $\lambda_{aa} = 542 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{ac} = 866 \text{ nm}$. Comparing these values with Fig. 1, we can see that they correspond to two emission bands (red line) under laser excitation. For graphene, the excitation and recombination processes will look as follows (Fig. 11) [37].

Figure 11. Nonequilibrium dynamics of electrons and luminescence of graphene [37].

The following follows from Fig. 11: after excitation of electrons from the deformation zone, which is a nonequilibrium nuclear subsystem, they are scattered by phonons over a period of 10-20 femtoseconds; then they are thermalized over a period of 300-500 femtoseconds: then recombination of electrons and holes occurs over a period of 3-10 picoseconds with subsequent emission of light quanta, i.e. hot luminescence occurs.

The deformation energy E_d of graphene is 1.62 eV (Table 3) and is transformed into hot luminescence, which is confirmed by Fig. 3.

Single-layer carbon nanotubes were experimentally obtained in 1991 by the Japanese physicist Iijima and have been studied to this day [38-40].

We will consider a nanotube obtained by rolling up a single-sheet graphene (see Fig. 3). When rolling up graphene, the chemical potential of the surface changes, and hence the elastic stresses σ_{is} (Table 2), changing the deformation energy E_d (Table 3). In [41], we proposed a model of graphite splitting, which is the opposite of graphene rolling up. The components of thermoelastic stresses along the radius r - σ_r and along the z - σ_z axis of the R(I) layer will be estimated using the known equations:

$$\sigma_r = -2G \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r}. \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_z = -2G \frac{\partial T}{\partial z}. \quad (8)$$

To calculate the stresses σ_{is} in the R(I) layer, when the graphite splitting process is in progress, we come to a problem with a moving phase boundary, which is

called the Stefan problem. In this case, the non-stationary heat conduction equation in a moving cylindrical coordinate system moving according to the law $\beta(t)$ has the form:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = D \cdot \left[\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) \right], \quad (9)$$

where D is the thermal diffusivity.

The thermal expansion coefficient of graphene has a minimum at room temperature and is $-3.7 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$, which in absolute value is three times greater than the thermal expansion coefficient of graphite in the plane at the same temperature ($1.3 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$).

Solving the Stefan problem for a finite cylinder (nanotube), we obtain [41]:

$$\check{N}(r, z, t) = \frac{D^{3/2} \cdot \check{N}_0}{\pi^2} J_0 \left(\frac{2r}{R} \right) \cdot \frac{t}{z\beta(t)}, \quad (10)$$

where $J_0(2r/R)$ is the zero-order Bessel function; R is the radius of the cylinder (nanotube).

Finally, for elastic stresses and deformation energy at $r = z$, we have:

$$\sigma_z = \chi \cdot \acute{L}_{\check{a}} = \mu \cdot J_1 \left(\frac{2z}{R} \right), \quad (11)$$

where $\mu = \text{const} \approx E_d/2 = 0.81 \text{ eV}$ (Fig. 2a).

Equation (11) shows the dependence of the deformation energy on the cylinder radius, which is shown in Fig. 12a. Fig. 12b shows the dependence of the chemical potential on the radius value for single-layer nanotubes, taken from [42].

Figure 12. Bessel functions (a); dependence of chemical potential on the radius value for single-walled nanotubes (b) [42].

The chemical potential of graphene is equal to its Fermi energy E_F and is determined by the deformation energy. Therefore, all previous considerations regarding the luminescence of carbon nanotubes should be valid.

Conclusion

According to the generally accepted expression of Harris P., carbon materials, including graphene and nanotubes, are new materials of the 21st century. This is especially relevant for space technology, the nuclear industry, and especially for photonics - light-emitting devices, optical modulators, optical interconnects and optical probing

The model of luminescence of graphite, graphene and nanotubes proposed by us opens a new page in the study of carbon materials.

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